

Modeling airbursts from comets, asteroids, and nuclear detonations: shock metamorphism, meltglass, and microspherules: Supporting Information

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Supporting information

Earth Impact Effects program, Input data

<https://impact.ese.ic.ac.uk/ImpactEarth/ImpactEffects>¹

Asteroid, 80-m

Input:

Projectile diameter: 80.00 meters
Projectile Density: 1500 kg/m³
Impact Velocity: 17.00 km/s
Impact Angle: 90 degrees
Target Density: 2500 kg/m³
Target Type: Sedimentary Rock

Results:

Energy before atmospheric entry: 5.81e+16 Joules = 13.9 MegaTons TNT
Projectile begins to breakup at an altitude of 72500 meters
Projectile bursts into a cloud of fragments at an altitude of 662 meters
The residual velocity of the projectile fragments after airburst is 1.73 km/s
The energy of the airburst is 5.75e+16 Joules = 13.7 MegaTons.
Average recurrence interval = 1700 years
No crater is formed, although large fragments may strike the surface.

Air Blast:

The air blast will arrive approximately 2.84 seconds after impact.
Peak Overpressure: 1.46e+07 to 2.92e+07 Pa
Max wind velocity: 3060 m/s
Sound Intensity: 143 dB

Comet, 100-m

Input:

Projectile diameter: 100.00 meters
Projectile Density: 1032 kg/m³
Impact Velocity: 30.00 km per second
Impact Angle: 90 degrees
Target Density: 2500 kg/m³
Target Type: Sedimentary Rock

Results:

Energy before atmospheric entry: $2.43\text{e}+17$ joules = 58.1 MegaTons TNT
Projectile begins to breakup at an altitude of 89200 meters
Projectile bursts into a cloud of fragments at an altitude of 203 meters
The residual velocity of the projectile fragments after the burst is 1.78 km/s
The energy of the airburst is $2.42\text{E}+17$ Joules = 57.9 MegaTons.
Average recurrence interval = 2500 years
No crater is formed, although large fragments may strike the surface.

Air Blast:

The air blast will arrive approximately 869 milliseconds after impact.
Peak Overpressure: $5.89\text{e}+08$ to $1.18\text{e}+09$ Pa
Max wind velocity: 19500 m/s
Sound Intensity: 175 dB

Asteroid, 140-m

Input:

Distance from Impact: 193.00 meters
Projectile diameter: 140.00 meters
Projectile Density: 530 kg/m^3
Impact Velocity: 51.00 km/s
Impact Angle: 90 degrees
Target Density: 2500 kg/m
Target Type: Sedimentary Rock

Results:

Energy before atmospheric entry: $9.9\text{e}+17$ Joules = 23.7 MegaTons TNT
Projectile begins to breakup at an altitude of 108000 meters
Projectile bursts into a cloud of fragments at an altitude of 193 meters
The residual velocity of the projectile fragments after the burst is 0.988 km/s
The energy of the airburst is $9.90\text{e}+17$ Joules = 23.6 MegaTons.
Average recurrence interval = 7400 years
No crater is formed, although large fragments may strike the surface.

Air Blast:

The air blast will arrive approximately 827 milliseconds after impact.
Peak Overpressure: $1.92\text{e}+09$ to $3.85\text{e}+09$ Pa
Max wind velocity: 35300 m/s = 79000 mph
Sound Intensity: 186 dB

Ansys Autodyn, Input data

Materials: Trinity airburst

Because of cell-size limitations and to enhance visibility, the dimensions of the nuclear bomb and tower leg widths are several times larger than actual. However, the bomb and tower material density and the TNT-equivalent energy are the same.

Autodyn, Trinity, Material Name - BOMB

Equation of State Shock
Reference density 5.00000E-01 (g/cm³)
Gruneisen coefficient 2.32000E+00 (none)
Parameter C1 2.48000E+03 (m/s)
Parameter S1 1.53000E+00 (none)
Parameter Quadratic S2 0.00000E+00 (s/m)
Relative volume, VE/V0 0.00000E+00 (none)
Relative volume, VB/V0 0.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter C2 0.00000E+00 (m/s)
Parameter S2 0.00000E+00 (none)
Reference Temperature 3.00000E+02 (K)
Specific Heat 1.08000E+02 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength Steinberg Guinan
Shear Modulus 8.67000E+07 (kPa)
Yield Stress 4.00000E+05 (kPa)
Maximum Yield Stress 1.68000E+06 (kPa)
Hardening Constant 2.00000E+03 (none)
Hardening Exponent 1.60000E-01 (none)
Derivative dG/dP 3.00000E+00 (none)
Derivative dG/dT -6.79730E+04 (kPa/K)
Derivative dY/dP 1.38400E-02 (none)
Melting Temperature 1.71000E+03 (K)
Failure None
Erosion None
Material Cutoffs -
Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.00000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)

Reference: "Equation of State and Strength Properties of Selected Materials". Steinberg D.J. LLNL. Feb 1991

Autodyn, Trinity, Material Name - AIR

Equation of State Ideal Gas
Reference density 1.22500E-03 (g/cm³)
Gamma 1.40000E+00 (none)
Adiabatic constant 0.00000E+00 (none)
Pressure shift 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Reference Temperature 2.88200E+02 (K)
Specific Heat 7.17600E+02 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength None
Failure None
Erosion None
Material Cutoffs -
Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.00000E+07 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference: "Thermodynamic and Transport Properties of Fluids, SI Units", GFC Rogers, YR Mayhew

Autodyn, Trinity, Material Name - SAND

Equation of State Compaction
Reference density 2.64100E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #1 1.67400E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #2 1.73950E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #3 1.87380E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #4 1.99700E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #5 2.14380E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #6 2.25000E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #7 2.38000E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #8 2.48500E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #9 2.58500E+00 (g/cm³)
Density #10 2.67130E+00 (g/cm³)
Pressure #1 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Pressure #2 4.57700E+03 (kPa)
Pressure #3 1.49800E+04 (kPa)
Pressure #4 2.91510E+04 (kPa)
Pressure #5 5.91750E+04 (kPa)
Pressure #6 9.80980E+04 (kPa)

Pressure #7 1.79443E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure #8 2.89443E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure #9 4.50198E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure #10 6.50660E+05 (kPa)
 Unloading method Linear
 Density (Soundspeed) #1 1.67400E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #2 1.74560E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #3 2.08630E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #4 2.14680E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #5 2.30000E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #6 2.57200E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #7 2.59800E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #8 2.63500E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #9 2.64100E+00 (g/cm3)
 Density (Soundspeed) #10 2.80000E+00 (g/cm3)
 Soundspeed #1 2.65200E+02 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #2 8.52100E+02 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #3 1.72170E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #4 1.87550E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #5 2.26480E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #6 2.95610E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #7 3.11220E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #8 4.60000E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #9 4.63400E+03 (m/s)
 Soundspeed #10 4.63400E+03 (m/s)
 Strength MO Granular
 Pressure (P-Y) #1 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #2 3.40100E+03 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #3 3.48980E+04 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #4 1.01324E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #5 1.84650E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #6 5.00000E+05 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #7 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #8 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #9 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Pressure (P-Y) #10 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #1 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #2 4.23500E+03 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #3 4.46950E+04 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #4 1.24035E+05 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #5 2.26000E+05 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #6 2.26000E+05 (kPa)
 Yield Stress (P-Y) #7 0.00000E+00 (kPa)

Yield Stress (P-Y) #8 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (P-Y) #9 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (P-Y) #10 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Density (D-Y) #1 1.67400E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #2 1.74570E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #3 2.08630E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #4 2.14680E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #5 2.30000E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #6 2.57200E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #7 2.59800E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #8 2.63500E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #9 2.64100E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-Y) #10 2.80000E+00 (g/cm3)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #1 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #2 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #3 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #4 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #5 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #6 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #7 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #8 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #9 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Yield Stress (D-Y) #10 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Density (D-G) #1 1.67400E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #2 1.74570E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #3 2.08630E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #4 2.14680E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #5 2.30000E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #6 2.57200E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #7 2.59800E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #8 2.63500E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #9 2.64100E+00 (g/cm3)
Density (D-G) #10 2.80000E+00 (g/cm3)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #1 7.69000E+04 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #2 8.69400E+05 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #3 4.03170E+06 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #4 4.90690E+06 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #5 7.76900E+06 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #6 1.48009E+07 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #7 1.65710E+07 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #8 3.67180E+07 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #9 3.73470E+07 (kPa)
Shear Modulus (D-G) #10 3.73470E+07 (kPa)

Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -1.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion Geometric Strain
 Erosion Strain 2.00000E+00 (none)
 Type of Geometric Strain Instantaneous
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.00000E+07 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: Laine L.,Sandvik A.,"Derivation of mechanical properties for sand",4th
 SILOS,CI-Premier LTD,p361 -367

Autodyn, Trinity, Material Name - TOWER

Equation of State Shock
 Reference density 7.90000E+00 (g/cm3)
 Gruneisen coefficient 2.32000E+00 (none)
 Parameter C1 2.48000E+03 (m/s)
 Parameter S1 1.53000E+00 (none)
 Parameter Quadratic S2 0.00000E+00 (s/m)
 Relative volume, VE/V0 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Relative volume, VB/V0 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter C2 0.00000E+00 (m/s)
 Parameter S2 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Reference Temperature 3.00000E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 1.08000E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength Steinberg Guinan
 Shear Modulus 8.67000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 4.00000E+05 (kPa)
 Maximum Yield Stress 1.68000E+06 (kPa)
 Hardening Constant 2.00000E+03 (none)
 Hardening Exponent 1.60000E-01 (none)
 Derivative dG/dP 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Derivative dG/dT -6.79730E+04 (kPa/K)
 Derivative dY/dP 1.38400E-02 (none)
 Melting Temperature 1.71000E+03 (K)

Failure None
Erosion None
Material Cutoffs -
Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-03 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.00000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)

Autodyn, Initial Conditions: Trinity airburst

Trinity, Airburst, Initial Condition Summary

Name : AIR
Material: AIR
Density 1.22E-03
Internal Energy 2.07E+05
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00 (Note: this is a 2D Euler grid with zero thickness)
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : NuclearEnergy
Material: BOMB
Density 1.98E+01
Internal Energy 1.25E+09
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Bomb
Material: BOMB
Density 5.00E-01
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Tower
Material: TOWER
Density 7.90E+00
Internal Energy 0.00E+00

Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Autodyn, 80-m asteroid, Materials (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

Autodyn, 80-m Asteroid, Material Name - Asteroid

Equation of State Tillotson
Reference density 1.50000E+00 (g/cm³)
Parameter A 4.55500E+07 (kPa)
Parameter B 1.60500E+06 (kPa)
Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es 2.75000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd 1.50000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature 1.80000E+02 (K)
Specific Heat 1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength von Mises
Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
Failure Hydro (Pmin)
Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal Yes
Crack Softening No
Stochastic failure No
Erosion None
Material Cutoffs -
Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference: -

Autodyn, 80-m Asteroid, Material Name - Earth

Equation of State Tillotson

Reference density 1.50000E+00 (g/cm³)
 Parameter A 4.55500E+07 (kPa)
 Parameter B 1.60500E+06 (kPa)
 Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
 Parameter es 2.75000E+08 (J/kg)
 Parameter esd 1.50000E+09 (J/kg)
 Reference Temperature 1.80000E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength von Mises
 Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: -

Autodyn, 80-m Asteroid, Material Name - AIR

Equation of State Ideal Gas
 Reference density 1.22500E-03 (g/cm³)
 Gamma 1.40000E+00 (none)
 Adiabatic constant 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Pressure shift 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Reference Temperature 2.88200E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 7.17600E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength None
 Failure None

Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-02 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+20 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: "Thermodynamic and Transport Properties of Fluids, SI Units", GFC Rogers, YR Mayhew

Autodyn, 80-m Asteroid, Material Name - Light-wt

Equation of State Tillotson
 Reference density 1.50000E+00 (g/cm³)
 Parameter A 4.55500E+07 (kPa)
 Parameter B 1.60000E+06 (kPa)
 Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
 Parameter es 2.75000E+08 (J/kg)
 Parameter esd 1.50000E+09 (J/kg)
 Reference Temperature 2.93000E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength von Mises
 Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal No
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+20 (m/s)

Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference: -

Autodyn, 80-m Asteroid, Material Name - Heavy-wt

Equation of State Tillotson
Reference density 3.30000E+00 (g/cm³)
Parameter A 1.00000E+08 (kPa)
Parameter B 3.54000E+07 (kPa)
Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es 2.50000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd 1.40000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature 2.88000E+02 (K)
Specific Heat 9.20000E+02 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength von Mises
Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
Failure Hydro (Pmin)
Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal No
Crack Softening No
Stochastic failure No
Erosion None
Material Cutoffs -
Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+20 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference: -

Autodyn, Initial Conditions: 80-m asteroid (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

80-m Asteroid, Initial Condition Summary

Name : Air
Material: AIR
Density 1.22E-03

Internal Energy 2.07E+05
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00 (Note: this is a 2D Euler grid with zero thickness)
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : AsteroidEnergy

Material: Asteroid
Density 1.50E+00
Internal Energy 1.14E+09
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 1.73E+03
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Asteroid

Material: Asteroid
Density 1.50E+00
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 1.70E+04
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Light, small

Material: Light-wt
Density 1.50E+00
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Heavy, tall

Material: Heavy-wt
Density 3.30E+00
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Autodyn, Materials: 100-m Comet (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

100-m Comet, Material Name - Comet

Equation of State Tillotson
Reference density 1.03200E+00 (g/cm³)
Parameter A 1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B 7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b 1.30000E+00 (none)

Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter e0 1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
 Parameter es 3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
 Parameter esd 1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
 Reference Temperature 5.00000E+01 (K)
 Specific Heat 1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength von Mises
 Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: -

100-m Comet, Material Name - Earth

Equation of State Tillotson
 Reference density 3.30000E+00 (g/cm3)
 Parameter A 1.00000E+08 (kPa)
 Parameter B 3.54000E+07 (kPa)
 Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
 Parameter es 2.50000E+08 (J/kg)
 Parameter esd 1.40000E+09 (J/kg)
 Reference Temperature 2.88000E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 9.20000E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength von Mises

Shear Modulus 4.50000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 6.19000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -6.88000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: -

100-m Comet, Material Name - AIR

Equation of State Ideal Gas
 Reference density 1.22500E-03 (g/cm³)
 Gamma 1.40000E+00 (none)
 Adiabatic constant 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Pressure shift 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Reference Temperature 2.88200E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 7.17600E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength None
 Failure None
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-02 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: "Thermodynamic and Transport Properties of Fluids, SI Units", GFC Rogers, YR Mayhew

Autodyn, Initial Conditions: 100-m Comet (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

Initial Condition Summary

Name : Air
Material: AIR
Density 1.22E-03
Internal Energy 2.07E+05
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00 (Note: this is a 2D Euler grid with zero thickness)
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Comet
Material: Comet
Density 1.03E+00
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 3.00E+04
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : CometEnergy
Material: Comet
Density 1.03E+00
Internal Energy 3.59E+09
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 1.78E+03
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Autodyn, Materials: 140-m Comet (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

140-m Comet, Material Name - Comet

Equation of State Tillotson
Reference density 5.30000E-01 (g/cm³)
Parameter A 1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B 7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b 1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0 1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es 3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd 1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature 5.00000E+01 (K)
Specific Heat 1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)

Strength von Mises
 Shear Modulus 5.30000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 3.44000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -2.75000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: -

140-m Comet, Material Name - Earth

Equation of State Tillotson
 Reference density 3.30000E+00 (g/cm3)
 Parameter A 1.00000E+08 (kPa)
 Parameter B 3.54000E+07 (kPa)
 Parameter a 5.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter b 6.00000E-01 (none)
 Parameter alpha 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter beta 5.00000E+00 (none)
 Parameter e0 1.00000E+07 (J/kg)
 Parameter es 2.50000E+08 (J/kg)
 Parameter esd 1.40000E+09 (J/kg)
 Reference Temperature 2.88000E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 9.20000E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength von Mises
 Shear Modulus 4.50000E+07 (kPa)
 Yield Stress 6.19000E+08 (kPa)
 Failure Hydro (Pmin)
 Hydro Tensile Limit -6.88000E+04 (kPa)
 Reheal Yes
 Crack Softening No
 Stochastic failure No
 Erosion None

Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-06 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: -

140-m Comet, Material Name - AIR

Equation of State Ideal Gas
 Reference density 1.22500E-03 (g/cm3)
 Gamma 1.40000E+00 (none)
 Adiabatic constant 0.00000E+00 (none)
 Pressure shift 0.00000E+00 (kPa)
 Reference Temperature 2.88200E+02 (K)
 Specific Heat 7.17600E+02 (J/kgK)
 Thermal Conductivity 0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
 Strength None
 Failure None
 Erosion None
 Material Cutoffs -
 Maximum Expansion 1.00000E-01 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor 1.00000E-04 (none)
 Minimum Density Factor (SPH) 2.00000E-01 (none)
 Maximum Density Factor (SPH) 3.00000E+00 (none)
 Minimum Soundspeed 1.00000E-02 (m/s)
 Maximum Soundspeed (SPH) 1.01000E+05 (m/s)
 Maximum Temperature 1.01000E+20 (K)
 Reference: "Thermodynamic and Transport Properties of Fluids, SI Units", GFC Rogers, YR Mayhew

Autodyn, Initial Conditions: 140-m Comet (Adapted from Saito^{2,3})

Initial Condition Summary

Name : Air
Material: AIR
Density 1.22E-03
Internal Energy 2.07E+05
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00 (Note: this is a 2D Euler grid with zero thickness)
X Velocity 0.00E+00
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : Comet
Material: Comet
Density 5.30E-01
Internal Energy 0.00E+00
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 5.10E+04
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

Name : CometEnergy
Material: Comet
Density 5.30E-01
Internal Energy 1.04E+10
Shell Thickness 0.00E+00
X Velocity 9.88E+02
Y Velocity 0.00E+00

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- 2 Saito, T., Kaiho, K., Abe, A., Katayama, M. & Takayama, K. Hypervelocity impact of asteroid/comet on the oceanic crust of the earth. *International Journal of Impact Engineering* **35**, 1770-1777 (2008).
- 3 Saito, T., Kaiho, K., Abe, A., Katayama, M. & Takayama, K. Numerical simulations of hypervelocity impact of asteroid/comet on the Earth. *International Journal of Impact Engineering* **33**, 713-722 (2006).